

The Coupling Constants Series and the Principle of Certainty - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of coupling constants magnitudes of the new 8T, and in particular the nature of net propagation, it is possible to present the principle of certainty. The certainty of not knowing anything about the process of propagation, its direction, location within the fermion cluster, curvature orientation, momenta and so on. The most intimate nature of nature is manifested in the primordial coupling series, but as it seems from the 8T, there is not anything beyond it. The principle of certainty indicate that all other physical quantities are certainly uncertain.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

The principle of certainty

We have presented two newer representations of the primorial. The first is the version concerning probability. we associate to each of the net curvature, a number which is unknown. For simplicity sake, we assumed it is the same for all coupling terms. This number represent the probability of net curvature emission. There are so many potential variants to such a number. We can be certain it does vary from term to term, and it could even vary over time. notice that the Primorial does not provide any data regarding the direction of propagation, momenta, time, there is the principle of certainty – it is certain that we won't be able to know those. The only certainty is the coupling term itself.

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) + \mathcal{M} \right) + P(A) \quad (2)$$

$$A \in \mathbb{P};$$

The next element in the series can only arise after a previous probability was satisfied, as it is a series. So the longer we develop, the smaller the probability to detect the boson as it is depended upon longer chain of events, with probability smaller than one. We can represent it in a simpler fashion by ignoring the constants:

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \quad (2.1)$$

Let $A \rightarrow \infty$

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \rightarrow 0 \quad (2.11)$$

There is additional version we presented, curvature spectra's. This version is based upon the multiplier of each term from the second and above, is reflecting the number of so-called "fields" of each interaction. The first coupling term has eight gluon fields:

$$8 + (1)$$

The second term has three fields, the massive W and Z bosons, in accordance to the right multiplier, marked in black:

$$[(8 * \mathbf{3}) + (3)] + 3$$

That is each interaction has Bosonic, net curvatures which differ from one another in certain orientation. In the process of propagation, it can be either particle that belong to the spectra. We can be certain that we will not be able to know which particle it is.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i=N_V} \Psi_i = N_V$$

$$F_R \# = \left(2^{\mathcal{M}} * \prod_{i=1}^{i=N_V} \Psi_i + (\mathcal{M}) \right) + N_V \quad (2)$$

Therefore, for each coupling term there is a set of elements, a spectrum of net curvature defined by the multiplier magnitude. Nature again does not provide us a way to know which kind of an element is going to be propagated, nor its direction, momenta and any other physical quantity. The principle of certainty is again manifested, the certainty of not knowing anything about nature beyond the structure and representations of the primordial coupling series.

It is almost as if nature is telling us that those quantities are not important, and that the most fundamental and intimate way to understand nature's nature, is the primordial series, there is nothing beyond it. No certainty of any sort, nor physical data of any sort. This is how nature really is.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)